

DIGITAL ECONOMY: STATE AND PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT

Jasur Jurayevich Qarshiyev

Denov Institute of entrepreneurship and pedagogy

Abstract. The study touches on a number of issues related to the development of the digital economy and the role of digital production. The main features and characteristic features of the digital economy at the present stage of development are considered. The authors determined the place of the digital economy in the economy of Uzbekistan and other countries, identified the main components of Industry 4.0 and the problems of its development.

Keywords: digital economy, internet, digitalization, virtual commerce.

After the Council on Legislative Support for the Development of the Digital Economy was established under the Government of Uzbekistan at the beginning of this year, a lot of questions arose about what the digital economy is in Uzbekistan and what its implementation will give. One of the generalized concepts of the digital economy is a system of economic and political, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital (computer) information and communication technologies. Digitalization of the economy will lead to the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Eng. The Fourth Industrial Revolution– is a predicted event, the mass introduction of cyber-physical systems into production (industry 4.0), servicing human needs, including everyday life, work and leisure [1]. The consequences of the implementation will cover all aspects of life: work, everyday life, politics, medicine, education and others.

The Internet has become an integral part of modern economic interaction. The digital economy has already penetrated into all sectors of the world economy and continues to develop actively [2]. In the era of the digital economy, which has a number of basic features, the main resource is information that is inexhaustible, and its main characteristic is accuracy (truthfulness) and timeliness. The main platform for the development of the digital economy is the virtual Internet, the "areas" of which are limitless. In the era of the market economy and in the time of Smith, it made sense to calculate the break-even point and the optimal size of firms and companies, for the digital economy - it does not matter: a company can be very small and at the same time develop successfully. The owner can be both the head and the executor of all stages of the company's work. The main "value" in the digital economy is the customer – who becomes the main one in the process of economic activity, because without him there is no sense in it itself. The customer chooses the product relying on advice, personal experience and advertising, the seller does not have the opportunity to personally contact the buyer. At the same time, advertising still has its own weight, only it is already Internet advertising, Internet fashion, Internet friends, Internet hobbies, etc.

And what does the digital economy include today? The main components of the digital economy for the Russian Federation today are consumption, investment, government spending, exports and imports. The largest share in the total volume of the digital economy is consumption as a form of virtual commerce. In recent years, the share of e-commerce has grown by 35-40%, in total retail sales it is about 5%, but still very little compared to the G20 countries. Virtual commerce is most widespread in the segments of household appliances and electronics, clothing and footwear, furniture and household goods. These categories account for 80% of the

e-commerce market in Russia. The market of virtual food products in the Russian Federation is gaining momentum, especially in large cities. Sensing the potential of the online segment, a number of large offline retailers already have, or are launching services for the sale and delivery of food at home. Instagram facet of the digital economy is defined by four trends: mobile technologies, business analytics, cloud computing and social media; globally, social networks such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, etc. This means that when forming a national segment, it is important to use their capabilities [3]. In recent years, such Internet-dependent markets have also been actively developed: tourism, games and esports, media and banking services, etc. Currently, these markets together account for about 50% of the total volume of e-commerce. The gradual digitalization of the mass segment is changing the nature of online consumption. In the segment of tourism and travel, the transition from online booking of tickets to a full-fledged selection, comparison and payment of tours is striking. In the segment of banking services, personal accounts replace standing in line at the bank's cash desk to pay utility bills, replenish the phone, pay for loans, etc. Import-export operations related to the digitalization of the economy show a slight increase. At the same time, a significant share of imports falls on China (a vivid example of this is the AliExpress website) and accounts for about 50% of all transactions.

In total, 85 states were included in the BCG rating. The leader of 2015 was Denmark, which scored 213 points. The second place went to Luxembourg (212 points), and the third — to Sweden (208). Also in the top five were South Korea (205) and the Netherlands (198). Cameroon closes the rating with an index of 12 points. The calculation of the BCG digitalization index is based on the dynamics of the growth of online spending of the population and user activity. However, like

most indices, the BCG digitalization index is a statistical indicator that has a share of conditionality. A large proportion of the population of our country are people over 45 years old, with secondary education, living in small towns. Such citizens often do not know how to use Internet services in order to purchase goods or pay for services, therefore, the level of digitalization will be lower than in a country with more active users. Finally, it should be noted that the digital economy is the future of the country's economic development, it is a new stage in the development of economic thought, production and consumption systems, it is a direct bridge to the era of space technologies and the virtual future.

References

1. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (Internet resource)
https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Четвертая_промышленная_революция
2. Andreeva E.Yu., Filchakova V.D. Digital economy of the future, Industry 4.0 // Applied mathematics and fundamental informatics. - 2016. - No. 3. - pp. 214-218.
3. Panshin B. Digital economy: features and development trends / Science and Innovation. - Publishing house "Belarusian Science" Minsk. - T. 3. – № 157. – 2016. – Pp. 17-20
4. Digital economy and "Industry 4.0": problems and prospects (industry-2017) Proceedings of a scientific and practical conference with international participation Editor: A.V. Babkin. "St. Petersburg Polytechnic University of Peter the Great" - 2017– - 685 p.